

Dihydroisocoumarins. Part III. Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin

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Synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III) is described.

In previous papers of this series, the syntheses of 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin¹ and 3,4-dihydro-6,7-dimethoxyisocoumarin² have been reported. This communication presents the synthesis of the third isomer, 3,4-dihydro-5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III).

The synthesis was effected by a seven-stage process from 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (Ia), prepared earlier by Banerjee and Chaudhury³. It was converted successively into 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoyl chloride (Ib) and *o*-diazo-2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitroacetophenone (Ic). The Wolff rearrangement of the latter with ammonia and silver oxide furnished 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetamide (Id). Transformation of the amide into 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetic acid (Ie) by the action of nitrous acid was not altogether satisfactory as only a part of the amide was converted into the acid. Hydrolysis of the amide, however, with orthophosphoric acid at 130° afforded (Ie) in satisfactory yield. Esterification with diazomethane yielded methyl 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetate (If).

(I)

(II)

(III)

I a: R = COOH. I d: R = CH₂CONH₂.
 I b: R = COCl. I e: R = CH₂COOH.
 I c: R = COCHN₂. I f: R = CH₂COOMe.

We were unable to prepare the nitro-ester (If) directly from the *o*-nitrodiazoketone (Ic) by the Wolff rearrangement with methanol and silver oxide. An unidentified crystalline solid, C₁₀H₁₀O₆N, m.p 95-96°, was obtained as the major product, whereas the

1. Banerjee and Chaudhury, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 4344.
 2. Srivastava and Chaudhury, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 998.
 3. *Ibid.*, 1959, 36, 257.

desired ester (If) was isolated only in traces. Similar difficulties were experienced in the preparation of methyl 2-nitrohomoveratrate'. No instance of converting *o*-nitro-acid directly to its homologous methyl ester by the Arndt-Eistert synthesis could be found in the literature. It is presumed that the Wolff rearrangement of *o*-nitrodiazoketones with methanol and silver oxide does not take the normal course; we propose to investigate the reaction in detail.

Methyl 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetate (If) was reduced with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by sodium dithionite, in accordance with the procedure adopted for the reduction of methyl 2-nitrohomoveratrate' to furnish 2,5-dimethoxy-5-aminophenethyl alcohol (II), isolated as its hydrochloride. Finally, diazotisation of the amine hydrochloride, conversion into the nitrile (which was not purified), and alkaline hydrolysis followed by acidification afforded 3,4-dihydro-5, 8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III).

*EXPERIMENTAL

2,5-Dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoyl Chloride (Ib).—2,5-Dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (5.0 g.) in dry CS_2 (85 ml) was refluxed on a water bath with PCl_5 (5.0 g.) for 2 hours, resulting in a deep red solution. The filtered solution on cooling deposited the acid chloride (3.5 g., 64.5%) as yellow needles, m.p. 109° (decomp.). The product without further purification was used for the next stage.

The anilide was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 201°. (Found: C, 60.1; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{14}O_5N_2$ requires C, 59.6; H, 4.6%.)

A solution of the acid chloride in minimum dry methanol, when kept overnight in an ice-chest, deposited methyl 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoate, crystallised from methanol as yellow irregular prisms, m.p. 122°, undepressed on admixture with a sample prepared earlier³ by the action of ethereal diazomethane on 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (Ia).

ω-Diazo-2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitroacetophenone (Ic).—A solution of the foregoing acid chloride (8.5 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (20 ml) was added dropwise to a cooled (0-5°) stirred solution of diazomethane in ether (200 ml) (from nitrosomethylurea, 20.0 g.). The product (Ic) separating from the reaction solution was collected next day (7.1 g.) and crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether as yellow needles (6.9 g., 82%), m.p. 130-31° (decomp.). (Found: C, 48.2; H, 3.9. $C_{16}H_{14}O_5N_3$ requires C, 47.8; H, 3.6%.)

2,5-Dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetamide (Id).—A solution of the above diazoketone (3.0 g.) in dioxane (50 ml) was treated with ammonia (30 ml; *d*, 0.88) and aqueous silver nitrate (9 ml, 10%) at 50°. After 1½ hours, when the evolution of nitrogen had subsided, aqueous silver nitrate (5 ml, 10%) and ammonia (3 ml; *d*, 0.88) were added, the bath temperature being raised to 55-60° and maintained for 1½ hours more. The reaction mixture was again treated with silver nitrate (3 ml, 10%) and ammonia (3 ml; *d*, 0.88), the bath temperature now being raised to and maintained at 60-65° for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was then refluxed for 15 minutes with a little charcoal and filtered hot. The yellow needles of (Id)

*All m.p.'s are uncorrected. Petroleum ether used had b.p. 60-80°. Microanalyses by Dr. Gore, University of Bombay.

immediately separated. The crude product was next dissolved in a large volume of boiling acetone-methanol (2:1; 500 ml), cooled, and filtered from traces of silver oxide; the filtrate, on concentration to a small bulk (75 ml) and cooling, deposited the *amide* in yellow needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 220-21°. A further amount (0.5 g.), recovered by concentrating the mother liquor and adding a little petroleum ether, raised the yield of the *amide* to 68%. Recrystallisations from ethyl acetate furnished the pure specimen as yellow needles, m.p. 224°. (Found: C, 49.5; H, 4.8. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 50.0; H, 5.0%).

2,5-Dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetic Acid (Ic) : Method (a).—An ice-cold solution of the foregoing *amide* (2.0 g.) in H_2SO_4 (200 g., 50% v/v) was treated dropwise with aqueous sodium nitrite (40 ml, 5%) with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred further for 15 minutes. The yellow solid (1.85 g.) separating was collected and treated with warm dilute NaOH solution and filtered from the unchanged *amide*. The filtrate on acidification furnished the desired acid (Ic) (1.0 g., 54%). It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether in pale yellow silky needles, m.p. 215°. (Found: C, 49.3; H, 3.9. $C_{10}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 49.8; H, 4.5%).

Method (b).—A solution of the *amide* (Id) (3.0 g.) in orthophosphoric acid (40 ml; d , 1.75) was heated to 130°, when after 15-20 minutes the acid (Ic) started separating in clusters of silky needles; the reaction mixture was kept at 130° for 1 hour, cooled, and poured in ice water (150 ml). The precipitate was collected, dissolved in warm dilute NaOH solution, and filtered. The filtrate was added to excess of HCl (conc.) when the *nitro-acid* (Ic) separated. It was crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether in pale yellow silky needles (2.4 g., 80%), m.p. 214-15°, undepressed on admixture with the sample prepared as in (a).

Methyl 2,5-Dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetate (If).—To a cooled solution of the above acid (3.0 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) excess ethereal diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (5g.), was added slowly and the mixture kept overnight at room temperature. The solution was evaporated and the solid residue crystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether to afford the ester (If) as yellow rectangular prisms, yield 2.6 g. (83%), m.p. 120°. (Found: C, 51.4; H, 4.9. $C_{11}H_{13}O_6N$ requires C, 51.7; H, 5.1%).

2,5-Dimethoxy-6-aminophenethyl Alcohol (II).—A solution of the foregoing *nitro-ester* (1.4 g.) in dry tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of $LiAlH_4$ (0.5 g.) in dry ether (50 ml), cooled to -15°, and left overnight at room temperature. The unchanged $LiAlH_4$ and the complex were decomposed by careful portionwise addition of ice water (30 ml) followed by 2N- H_2SO_4 (50 ml). The deep red ether layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 50 ml). The combined extract was dried (K_2CO_3) and evaporated to a deep red gummy residue, which was dissolved in warm methanol (30 ml). Water (25 ml) was added to turbidity and the solution was cleared by addition of tetrahydrofuran (30 ml). Sodium dithionite (3.0 g.) was added in portions when the red colour of the solution was partially discharged. The reaction mixture was next gently refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with portionwise addition of water (15 ml) to dissolve the dithionite, resulting in a pale yellow solution. Most of the organic solvents distilled and the cooled aqueous solution was extracted with ethyl acetate (5 × 50 ml); the extract was dried (K_2CO_3) and concentrated under reduced pressure to a small bulk (50 ml). It was chilled in a freezing mixture and dry hydrogen chloride bubbled through. The *alcohol* separated as

its hydrochloride (0.7 g.). Sublimation in *vacuo* (bath temp. 165-70°/0.5 mm) yielded the pure product as colorless needles (0.65 g.), m.p. 220° (decomp.). (Found: C, 50.9; H, 7.1. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3NCl$ requires C, 51.4; H, 6.8%).

3,4-Dihydro-5,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III).—The above amine hydrochloride (0.6 g.) in HCl (0.6 ml; *d*, 1.16) and water (14 ml) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.18 g.) in water (1.5 ml) at 0°. After neutralisation with anhydrous sodium carbonate, the diazonium solution was added to a solution of potassium cyanide (0.6 g.), nickel chloride (0.48 g.), and anhydrous sodium carbonate (0.15 g.) in water (10 ml) at 10° with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 2 hours and then heated at 70° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The cooled reaction mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 50 ml), the extract dried (K_2CO_3), and the solvent evaporated to give a dark solid residue. It was refluxed with aqueous KOH (30 ml, 10%) for 7 hours, cooled, acidified with HCl (conc.), filtered, and extracted with chloroform (3 × 50 ml). The dried (Na_2SO_4) extract on evaporation left a gum which solidified in an ice chest. It was dissolved in benzene (25 ml), chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (15 × 1 cm), and eluted with benzene. Evaporation of the solvent gave an oil which gradually solidified in the ice chest. Recrystallisations from benzene-petroleum ether afforded the *isocoumarin* as colorless prisms (0.2 g.), m.p. 99°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 5.7. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.4; H, 5.8%). The infrared spectrum (chloroform solvent) had a band at 5.87 μ . (conjugated δ -lactone).

Wolff Rearrangement of ω -Diazo-2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitroacetophenone (Ic).—A mixture of dry methanol (100 ml) and silver oxide (0.5 g.) was refluxed on a water bath for 15 minutes when a silver mirror was formed. After cooling, the diazoketone (3.0 g.) was added, the temperature being maintained at 50-55°. The evolution of nitrogen subsided after 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours; silver oxide (0.3 g.) was added and the bath temperature held at 50-55° for 1 $\frac{1}{2}$ hours more. It was again treated with silver oxide (0.2 g.), the bath temperature now being raised to and maintained at 55-60° for 1 hour. The filtered reaction mixture on evaporation left a gummy residue which solidified on cooling. It was dissolved in benzene (25 ml) and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (35 g.). Elution with benzene and subsequent evaporation of the solvent left an oil which soon solidified to a pale yellow crystalline mass (1.5 g.), m.p. 85-90°. Fractional crystallisations from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether yielded *two* products: (a) a small amount of methyl 2,5-dimethoxy-6-nitrophenylacetate, m.p. 119-20°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen prepared as above; (b) pale yellow plates (1.0 g.), m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 50.4; H, 4.2; N, 5.6%). Empirical formula calculated: $C_{10}H_{10}O_6N$. The compound reduces Tollen's reagent, but does not reduce Fehling's solution. It undergoes extensive decomposition with boiling dilute hydrochloric acid.